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EGFR silencing during metastasis to the lung.

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EGFR transcriptional dynamics during transformation and progression of cancer as a disease in humans are unique (1-3). We describe here apparent EGFR silencing (4, 5) during metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a component of the metastatic program identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer.

Results

Figure 1: EGFR is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	6.34E-02	1.115	1.856342	2.0690186	935.99	EGFR	4583/22997	80.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of the epidermal growth factor receptor, encoded by *EGFR* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of EGFR changed more than 80% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of EGFR messenger RNA in lung metastases in this metastatic setting.

II. Cell culture model of lung metastatic propensity; human breast cancer.

n=2 MDA-PAR lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, low metastatic potential)

n=2 MDA-LM2 lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, high metastatic potential)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1956	2.92E-02	0.19	2.180756	0.4135129	320.62	EGFR	690/10554	93.5

Through measurement of total transcription in cells with low metastatic potential as compared to cells with high metastatic potential using the MDA-LM2 model derived from MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, we validated differential expression of EGFR in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of EGFR here changed more than nearly 95% of the lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 10,554 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating instead lower expression of EGFR messenger RNA in breast cancer cells with high potential to metastasize to the lungs.

1 Thus, differential and decreased expression of EGFR defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in
2 human breast cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 We described here EGFR silencing during metastasis to the lung in breast cancer, in humans with
5 breast cancer in vivo and in a mouse model of lung metastasis.

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21 **Methods**

22 We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in
23 metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE186637, in
24 human breast cancer cells for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published
25 and public) and R-based computational methods.

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